

ABDOMINAL MULTI-ORGAN LOCALIZATION ON CONTRAST-ENHANCED CT BASED ON MAXIMUM A POSTERIORI PROBABILITY AND MINIMUM VOLUME OVERLAP

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ABSTRACT

Multi-organ localization is required for many automated abdominal organ analysis tasks. We recently developed an automated organ localization method, which used an MAP framework, and applied it to non-contrast CT images. This method failed to localize smaller organs such as kidneys in some image data because it did not respect the spatial relationship among multiple organs. To address the problem, we extend the framework by modeling the inter-organ spatial relations using a minimum volume overlap constraint and incorporating it into the MAP framework. The method was validated on 17 contrast-enhanced CT images and identified correctly the liver, spleen, pancreas and kidneys in all data sets. The new method is more robust to organ pose variations, computationally fast, and improved significantly the localization of kidneys.

INDEX TERMS: *contrast-enhanced CT, liver, spleen kidney, localization, maximum a posteriori probability.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Computed tomography (CT) is commonly adopted for imaging abdominal organs for the purpose of disease diagnosis and pre-operative planning and guidance. For abdominal organs, their volumes, shapes and enhancement can be indicators of disorders. Because of the complex spatial and physiological relationship and interactions among abdominal organs, it is beneficial to detect and analyze these organs together.

Abdominal multi-organ segmentation is a challenging task because the sizes, shapes, and locations of the organs vary significantly in different subjects. Moreover, these organs have similar appearance in CT images and are in close proximity to each other. Several methods have been proposed for the segmentation of individual abdominal organs from contrast-enhanced CT images especially for the liver [1,2,3,4], and, recently, the simultaneous segmentation of multiple organs [5,6,7]. Most of these methods relied on prior knowledge of the organs, for example probabilistic

atlases [8,9] and active shape models [1,4] constructed from training data.

The successful segmentation of abdominal organs uniformly requires a good initial localization, which is generally performed interactively [5,7,8]. To automate the organ localization process, Okada et al. [1] initialized the liver segmentation by estimating the abdominal cavity, but it is not certain how well this approach works for smaller organs, such as kidneys and spleen. Yao and Summers [10] used a statistical location model, but the method was limited to estimating only the organ locations without considering the orientations and sizes. Yao et al. [11] simultaneously detected multi-organ locations by finding bounding boxes using principal component analysis and a probabilistic atlas. Due to the large variability of abdominal organ sizes and orientations, however, the location alone cannot completely localize the organs in the abdomen, and thus is not sufficient to accurately initialize other image analysis tasks. Seifert et al. [12] estimated the organ location, orientation, and size using automatically detected anatomical landmarks, semantics and machine learning techniques, but the technical details of the method are not clear.

Recently, we proposed an automated abdominal organ localization method [13] using a maximum a posteriori (MAP) framework. Compared with other methods, the technique localized abdominal organs by finding the full organ poses, which includes not only locations, but also orientations and sizes. Organ poses enable a more accurate localization and thus a better initialization for segmentation and other image processing tasks. The method was initially applied only to non-contrast CT data, although contrast-enhanced CT is generally used in abdominal diagnosis and provides better organ visualization. Moreover, the method did not take advantage of the spatial relationships of the organs. As a result, the technique erroneously localized the kidneys partially within the liver or spleen on several datasets.

To address these problems, we developed a method that extends the MAP framework in [13] to include inter-organ relations using a minimum volume overlap constraint and models the enhancement of abdominal organs. The

technique was validated on 17 contrast-enhanced CT data and showed more robust results.

2. METHODS

We focus on the localization of five abdominal organs: liver, spleen, left and right kidneys, and pancreas. Our method first computes statistical information from a set of N training images $\{\mathbf{I}_n\}_{n=1}^N$. The organs were manually segmented in each training image and statistically modeled by building a pose distribution model (OPDM), a probabilistic atlas (PA), and a probabilistic intensity profile (IP). The statistical knowledge was then used to organ poses in a subject image in a way similar to the MAP framework as in [13]. In addition, we introduce a minimum volume overlap term into the MAP formulation, which models the spatial inter-organ relationship and makes the method more robust to organ pose variations. The method is detailed as follows.

The a posteriori probability. For a given organ $O^{(j)}$, its pose $\Theta^{(j)}$ is defined using nine parameters, which include the location $\mathbf{c}=[c_x, c_y, c_z]$, orientation $\mathbf{v}=[v_x, v_y, v_z]$ (Euler angles), and scale $\mathbf{s}=[s_x, s_y, s_z]$. For a given abdominal subject CT image \mathbf{S} in which the organs are to be localized, the a posteriori probability of the pose of $O^{(j)}$ is

$$p(\Theta^{(j)} | \mathbf{S}, O^{(j)}) \propto p(\mathbf{S} | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)}) p(\Theta^{(j)} | O^{(j)}). \quad (1)$$

where the prior $p(\Theta^{(j)} | O^{(j)})$ and the conditional probability $p(\mathbf{S} | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)})$ are computed using the statistical knowledge from training data sets after abdomen normalization based on anatomical landmarks [13].

The abdomen normalization reduces the organ pose variability caused by the shape and size differences of abdominal cavities in different subjects. For this, the vertebrae and the ribs are automatically segmented and identified from the CT scans using the method in [10]. A bounding box is then defined around the abdominal cavity. One standard image (denoted as J_0) was chosen from the training images, and all the other images are then normalized to J_0 by aligning the abdominal bounding boxes. Details of abdominal normalization can be found in [13].

The prior $p(\Theta^{(j)} | O^{(j)})$ or OPDM models the organ pose distribution in the normalized abdomen. The OPDM of each organ was built independently. The pose of organ $O^{(j)}$ in the standard image J_0 was defined as the reference pose $\Theta_0^{(j)} = [\mathbf{c}_0^{(j)}, \mathbf{v}_0^{(j)}, \mathbf{s}_0^{(j)}]$ with $\mathbf{c}_0^{(j)}$ being the center of gravity, $\mathbf{v}_0^{(j)} = [0, 0, 0]$ representing the orientations in the three dimensions, and $\mathbf{s}_0^{(j)} = [1, 1, 1]$ being the scales. The poses of $O^{(j)}$ in every other training image is computed by registering the manual segmentation of $O^{(j)}$ of the image to that of J_0 using a nine-parameter linear transformation. The pose of $O^{(j)}$ in the n^{th} image is denoted as

$\Theta_n^{(j)} = [\mathbf{c}_n^{(j)}, \mathbf{v}_n^{(j)}, \mathbf{s}_n^{(j)}]$. The nine pose parameters are assumed independently distributed, and the OPDM can be estimated using Parzen windows [14],

$$p(\Theta^{(j)} | O^{(j)}) = \prod_{k=1}^9 p(\theta_k^{(j)} | O^{(j)}) = \prod_{k=1}^9 \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi h_k^{(j)}}} e^{-\frac{(\theta_k^{(j)} - \theta_{k,n}^{(j)})^2}{2h_k^{(j)}}}. \quad (2)$$

where $\theta_k^{(j)}$ for $k=1, \dots, 9$ are the 9 pose parameters, $\theta_{k,n}^{(j)}$ is the pose parameter value of organ $O^{(j)}$ computed from the n^{th} training image, and $h_k^{(j)}$ is the bandwidth and is estimated using the standard deviation of the sample data $\theta_{k,n}^{(j)}$ for $n=0, \dots, N-1$.

The conditional probability $p(\mathbf{S} | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)})$ for the given subject image \mathbf{S} uses PA and IP, which are computed for each organ from the training data as shown in [13]. The transformed PA, denoted as $p(\mathbf{x} | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)})$, models the organ location, and represents the probability that a point \mathbf{x} belongs to the organ $O^{(j)}$ for a given pose parameter $\Theta^{(j)}$. The IP, denoted as $p(u | O^{(j)})$, describes the probability that any voxel in $O^{(j)}$ takes an intensity value of u . After some mathematical manipulation, it is shown that

$$p(\mathbf{S} | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)}) = \exp\left(\sum_{m=1}^M h(u_m | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)}) \log p(u_m | O^{(j)})\right). \quad (3)$$

with $h(u_m | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)})$ being the conditional histogram

$$h(u_m | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)}) = \sum_{\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbf{V}} f(u_m, \mathbf{x}_i) p(\mathbf{x}_i | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)}), \quad (4)$$

$$\text{with } f(u_m, \mathbf{x}_i) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } u(\mathbf{x}_i) = u_m \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}.$$

The exponent in Eqn. (3) is the negative *cross entropy* between the two probability functions $h(u | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)})$ and $p(u | O^{(j)})$, and is denoted as H . Thus, the logarithm of the a posteriori probability can be written as:

$$C_{AP}(O^{(j)}) = -H(h(u | \Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)}), p(u | O^{(j)})) + \sum_{k=1}^9 \log p(\theta_k^{(j)} | O^{(j)}) \quad (5)$$

The volume overlap. Previous experiments on non-contrast CT images [13] showed that the maximization of C_{AP} failed to localize the kidneys in a few cases. The reason is that the kidneys are located close to neighboring organs (liver and spleen), and they have similar intensity profiles in the non-contrast images. Therefore the second term in (5), which comes from the OPDM, was not sufficient to guarantee that the MAP converge to the correct pose in some cases. As a result, the localized kidneys overlapped with the liver and spleen (see Fig. 1).

To prevent the localized organs from overlapping with each other, we explore the inter-organ spatial relationships. For the given pose parameters ($\Theta^{(j)}$) of all organs, the normalized volume overlap of organ $O^{(j)}$ with all other organs is defined as:

$$C_{VO}^{(j)} = \frac{\sum_{i \neq j} \sum_{x \in V} [p(x|\Theta^{(i)}, O^{(i)})p(x|\Theta^{(j)}, O^{(j)})]}{\sum_{x \in V} p(x|O^{(j)})}, \quad (6)$$

The denominator in (6) is the total volume of $O^{(j)}$ and is computed by adding up the PA at points x across the image volume V . By incorporating inter-organ relations in our method, the localization of abdominal organs is performed dependently instead of independently. Thus, we define a new cost function by combining the minimum volume overlap term in (6) with the logarithm of the a posteriori probability function in (5),

$$C = \sum_j C_{AP}^{(j)} - \lambda \sum_j C_{VO}^{(j)}, \quad (7)$$

where λ is a non-negative weighting parameter.

Fig. 1: An example showing that maximizing the a posteriori probability without inter-organ relations and enhancement fails to accurately localize the kidneys. The localization results of the left and right kidneys are shown in blue and orange, respectively, in axial views.

For each organ, the maximization of (7) is performed using the steepest descent method [15] in an iterative fashion. A multi-resolution strategy is adopted for efficient computation. At each iteration, the poses of the five organs are computed in sequential order: liver, spleen, left kidney, right kidney, and pancreas. This order is adopted because it was found from experiments that liver and spleen are more likely to be successfully localized because they have relatively larger sizes, so that their intermediate localization can be used to better constrain the localization of kidneys and pancreas through the minimum volume overlap term.

After the estimation of organ poses, the probabilistic atlas of each organ is transformed based on the computed pose and placed in the image volume to localize the organ.

3. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

We applied the method to 17 (six males, 11 females) patients' contrast-enhanced CT data. The images were collected on four types of CT scanners from three manufacturers with 1 mm slice thickness and 0.66-0.91 mm in-plane resolution. The five organs of interest were manually segmented from all images by a medical student supervised by a radiologist to create the ground truth. The symmetric volume overlap between the estimated organs and manual segmentations was measured using the Dice coefficient [16]. In all the experiments, the weighting parameter λ was set to 2.

To validate the method to localize five abdominal organs, the liver, spleen, left and right kidneys, and pancreas, 17 experiments were performed using a leave-one-out strategy. In each experiment, one dataset was picked as the subject image, and the remaining 16 datasets served as the training data. After localization, the estimated organ was then compared with the ground truth.

Fig. 2 shows the localization results on one typical data set using the minimum overlap (MO) method. For comparison, we repeated the experiments using the independent localization (IL) approach in [13], in which all the organs were independently localized without considering the inter-organ relations. The results of both approaches are presented in Table 1. The two methods produced similar results on the liver, and the MO method performed quantitatively better on all the other four organs. The non-parametric Wilcoxon sign rank test showed significant improvements for the localization of kidneys ($p < 0.05$). Qualitatively, all the five organs in all 17 experiments were successfully localized using the MO method. Using the IL approach, the right kidney was incorrectly localized on one data set; a large part of the right kidney was localized inside the liver, which resulted in a Dice coefficient of 0.24, as shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 2: The organ localization results, from left to right, on coronal, axial, and sagittal views of a contrast-enhanced data set. The liver is shown in blue, the spleen in green, the left kidney in orange, the right kidney in purple, and the pancreas in yellow.

Table 1: The average Dice coefficients between the organ localization results and manual segmentation on 17 experiments. The p-values of the Wilcoxon sign rank test comparing the results of the MO and IL methods are presented.

Method		Liver	Spleen	Left Kidney	Right Kidney	Pancreas
MO	Mean	0.80	0.65	0.75	0.79	0.42
	Std	0.03	0.06	0.05	0.03	0.15
IL	Mean	0.80	0.55	0.74	0.75	0.38
	Std	0.03	0.05	0.06	0.13	0.17
p-value		0.06	0.63	0.03	0.02	0.33

Table 2 shows the localization error for the five abdominal organs using the MO method. The technique performed best on the left and right kidneys, which had an average location error less than 3 mm. The location error of the liver, a much larger organ with variable shape, was less than 5 mm. The pancreas, a thin and long organ with very large shape variability across subjects, had the largest

localization error, especially in the y-axis. This is not surprising, as it is well known that the localization and segmentation of pancreas is very challenging because of the organ's high variability and its surrounding tissues of similar CT intensity.

Fig. 3: Illustration of the localization results of right kidney on one dataset in which the MO method succeeded and the IL method failed. The results are shown on several slices from the 3D image volume. The results of the MO method are shown in purple, those of the IL method in orange, while the overlapping results from the two methods are presented in yellow.

Table 2: The errors of organ location using the MO method.

Centroid (mm)	Liver	Spleen	Left Kidney	Right Kidney	Pancreas	
x	Mean	4.77	5.30	0.83	1.22	8.72
	Std	4.96	8.72	0.61	0.98	7.66
y	Mean	3.96	5.32	1.02	1.75	7.86
	Std	3.37	3.56	0.63	1.56	14.3
z	Mean	3.17	4.22	2.69	2.36	6.62
	Std	2.18	3.04	1.60	1.77	6.47

4. CONCLUSION

A method for automated multi-organ localization from abdominal contrast-enhanced CT images was presented. The method finds the locations, orientations, and scales of five abdominal organs by maximizing the a posteriori probabilities of organ poses. Additionally, the technique uses a minimum volume overlap constraint to model inter-organ relations. The constraint is combined with the logarithm of the a posteriori probability function to get a new cost function, which is optimized to determine the poses of multiple abdominal organs jointly. The method was

successfully applied to five abdominal organs, the liver, spleen, left and right kidneys, and pancreas.

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